

EUROPEAN ORGANIZATION FOR NUCLEAR RESEARCH

Beamtime request

TISD for molecular lanthanide beams

January 30, 2024

Wiktoria Wojtaczka¹, Mia Au², Cyril Bernerd², Katerina Chrysalidis², Thomas Elias Cocolios¹, Charlotte Duchemin², Paul Florian Giesel^{3,5}, Reinhard Heinke², Jake Johnson¹, Ralitsa Mancheva², Lukas Nies³, Daniel Lange^{3,4}, Christoph Schweiger^{3,4}, Edgar Reis², Ralf Erik Rossel², Sebastian Rothe²

¹*IKS, KU Leuven, Belgium*

²*SY-STI, CERN, Switzerland*

³*EP-SME, CERN, Switzerland*

⁴*Max-Planck-Institut für Kernphysik, Heidelberg, Germany*

⁵*Universität Greifswald, Greifswald, Germany*

Spokesperson: Wiktoria Wojtaczka wiktoria.wojtaczka@cern.ch

Contact person: Mia Au mia.au@cern.ch

Abstract: This target and ion source development beamtime request proposes to use a tantalum target in combination with a FEBIAD ion source to investigate the molecular beam formation of lanthanides.

1 Introduction

Tantalum targets can be used to produce lanthanide beams but in order to extract species with slow release times, such as terbium, the targets have to be pushed to extreme temperatures. This is especially true when it comes to medical isotope production that requires collections of the order of GBq/day of isotopes with minimum half-life of several hours. One way to volatilise the more refractory species is to introduce fluorine to the environment in order to form fluoride molecules which are often more volatile than their atomic counterparts [1]. Previous studies have explored injecting CF_4 to different target and ion source combinations via calibrated leaks, observing the formation of fluoride molecules and molecular ions of different species [2–4]. Extracting fluoride molecules could also potentially help to purify the beam by collecting on a sideband with fewer contaminants. This makes fluoride beams a promising potential avenue to provide beams to study more refractory lanthanides and to increase the experimental yields of more exotic isotopes that have not been accessible to study at ISOLDE so far. For nuclear medicine, this could facilitate more pre-clinical trials with terbium-based radiopharmaceuticals. Additionally, this approach could be advantageous for some other species that cannot be extracted from carbide targets due to their chemistry.

2 Motivation

As the experimental programmes at ISOLDE push the boundaries of the nuclide chart in the search for new physics, the demand for new radioactive beams grows. Those beams are progressively more challenging to produce and require technical developments of the target and ion source in order to meet the yield and purity requirements. One of the regions of the nuclide chart that has been getting more attention are lanthanides [5–12]. Tm and Lu are beams of interest for condensed matter physics, particularly for time differential perturbed gamma gamma angular correlation (TDPAC) [13]. Lu is expected to be obtained with high yields and beam purity through fluoride extraction as stated in [2, 4]. Additionally, there is a growing interest in proton emitters such as ^{145}Tm and $^{135,137}\text{Tb}$ which push the limits of what we know about the strong nuclear force that binds the nucleus together [9, 10].

Terbium is not only interesting from the nuclear physics point of view but also from the nuclear medicine side [6, 14–16]. With four isotopes displaying complementary decay characteristics, Tb is often described as one of the most promising elements for theranostics [17, 18]. Right now ^{149}Tb can only be produced in Europe at ISOLDE which would not be enough to supply clinical trials. Currently medical grade ^{149}Tb is produced through extraction of its precursor ^{149}Dy , which is much easier to produce as Dy has a lower boiling point and better release out of the target material. However, only 53% of the ^{149}gDy decays to the useful ^{149}gTb . In the past, ^{149}Tb was extracted directly however the yields were much lower than those obtained through Dy collection and decay feeding [19].

Terbium beams are particularly desirable but notoriously difficult to make. They are generally produced from tantalum foils which do not have the advantage of having a stable pore structure allowing fast diffusion and effusion of produced isotopes from the target material. Additionally, even if Tb does make it to the surface of the Ta foils, it could potentially

condense on any cold spots within the target unit which could be one of the contributing factors responsible for the low extraction yields. If this is true, one way to improve the yields would be to volatilise it, which can be done by extracting it as a molecule with a lower boiling point, for example as terbium fluoride. Trying to extract terbium through its fluoride sideband seems like the natural progression. There has been significant development in molecular extraction of actinides at ISOLDE [3] and there are many similarities between lanthanides and actinides, especially the difficulty when it comes to their extraction. Moreover, the technique of volatilising Tb through fluoride injection could be used at offline separators such as the MEDICIS facility to expand the supply of Tb currently available in Europe. In the near future, there are several emerging ISOL facilities, such as ISOL@MYRRHA [20] or TATTOOS@PSI [21], which aim to produce Tb for clinical and preclinical applications and would benefit from the development of Tb beams for nuclear medicine applications [22].

Initial investigation into the terbium fluoride beam was performed offline. The strongest sideband was identified as TbF_2 but diffusion out of the target material still remains unknown. An experiment was done at MEDICIS where $^{155}\text{TbF}_2$ beam was extracted with efficiency of $\sim 0.1\%$ which is promising but requires further development. This project highlights the symbiotic nature of the two facilities which can both profit from exploring terbium beam production further. Being able to replenish the target with isotopes at ISOLDE and run a series of measurements in different conditions would be invaluable in establishing best production conditions that could then be translated to MEDICIS, and other facilities in the future. Furthermore, it would allow us to obtain yields and release curves in different conditions. Since so many lanthanide contaminants are present on terbium mass from an irradiated tantalum target - e.g. CeO, LaO, Gd, Dy - it is essential that we gain a representative understanding of how to deliver pure beams in different conditions, especially for medical use where radionuclidic purity is essential in addition to good yield. This cannot be done in offline conditions due to changing inventory of the radionuclides in the target throughout the test. Similarly, using an external sample from a cyclotron would not be representative in this case since gadolinium targets are used for irradiation with low energy protons and the material undergoes chemical purification before the mass separation step. Additionally, finding good conditions at ISOLDE allows us to evaluate beam purity and proper conditions for producing other lanthanides of physics interest e.g. the Tm and Lu for the studies mentioned, as well as the proton emitters.

3 Method

In this investigation a tantalum target coupled to a hot plasma source will be used. For fluorination, CF_4 will be injected through a calibrated leak to gradually displace the buffer gas, in this case argon, to test different levels of fluorination. The target temperature will be varied from 1900°C to 2100°C and for each level of fluorination an anode scan from 0 to 250V will be performed. At each of these instances, chosen isotopes (to be determined) will be measured with ISOLTRAP multi-reflection time-of-flight mass spectrometer (MR-ToF MS) [23] to identify beam composition while the fast tapestation [24] can be used for measuring yields. The ISOLTRAP MR-TOF MS will be the main tool used for identification of beam composition at different target and ion source conditions. It is the only tool that has the ability to identify

stable isobaric contaminants on-line [25]. Evaluation of the presence and quantity of contaminants is essential for the eventual application of accelerator-produced Tb ion beams as a source of Tb for nuclear medicine. This will also allow for the determination of the release curve for terbium out of the target, which has never been measured before.

For long-lived species, collections are foreseen for offline characterisation with HPGe detectors. This is especially of interest for ^{149}Tb , ^{152}Tb and ^{155}Tb and isotopes of interest for TDPAC: ^{168}Tm and ^{172}Lu . Additionally, offline characterisation by alpha decay spectroscopy is foreseen for ^{149}Tb .

4 Summary of requested shifts

1 shift is requested to perform the initial characterisation of the region before and after fluorine injection using mass scans. We then request 17 shifts for a systematic study of the beam composition at different target conditions focusing on the lanthanide region, particularly terbium. We request one day (3 shifts) per each fluorination level, details are outlined in Table 1. Each time the fluorination level is changed, a mass scan up to TaF_4 would be used to check fluorine saturation in the target.

The species that will be most efficiently released and ionised under different conditions are mostly unknown. Therefore, this systematic study of ion beam composition as a function of target and ion source conditions will yield information of elemental selectivity under the conditions investigated, that could allow tailored beam delivery of different lanthanides. The temperature of both the target and the ion source, as well as the fluorine content play an important role on beam composition. Additionally, the electron bombardment in the ion source could potentially not only shift the ratios between different species of one element, but also by preferential breakup of some molecular species of certain elements could lead to identifying pure sidebands. Following the systematic studies, shifts are requested to measure yields and release of specific beams, to be identified during the systematic investigation. One of those beams will be terbium so that the yields can be compared to those obtained using laser ionised dysprosium for medical isotope production. In order to ensure the purity required for medical applications, we propose test collections of ^{149}Tb and the fluoride sidebands for offline yield characterisation with both gamma and alpha decay spectroscopy.

Additionally, we propose 3 shifts to perform an investigation into 'offline' irradiation conditions. Here we would like to cool the target and the ion source to 1000°C for extended irradiation (2-3 hours) before heating the target and observing the release of TbF_2 . The conditions might have to be adjusted compared to hot irradiation and the beam composition would be assessed using ISOLTRAP, especially in the case of the release being hindered.

	CF₄	Temperature	Mass scan	Anode scan	ISOLTRAP	Tapestation	Collections
Day 1	0	2000°C	1-260	0-250 in steps of 50V	TbO, Tb as control		
Day 2	30%	1900°C 2000°C	120-260	0-250 in steps of 50V	Tb all F sidebands	Tb yields all F sidebands	
Day 3	50%	2000°C	120-260	0-250 in steps of 50V	Tb all F sidebands	Tb yields all F sidebands	
Day 4	70%	1900°C 2000°C	120-260	0-250 in steps of 50V	Tb all F sidebands	Tb yields all F sidebands	
Day 5	100%	2000°C	120-260	0-250 in steps of 50V	Tb all F sidebands	Tb yields all F sidebands	Tb, Tm, Lu all F sidebands
Day 6	best %	1900°C 2000°C 2100°C	1-260	0-260 in steps of 20V	Tb all F sidebands	Tb yields all F sidebands	Tb all F sidebands
Day 7 'offline'	best %	1900°C 2000°C 2100°C	1-260	0-260 in steps of 20V	Tb release Tb, TbF, TbF ₂	Tb sideband ID	Tb all F sidebands

Table 1: Foreseen measurements schedule.

References

- [1] U. Köster et al. (Im-)possible ISOL beams. *The European Physical Journal Special Topics*, 150:285–291, 2007.
- [2] E. Hagebø et al. “New production systems at ISOLDE”. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 70(1-4):165–174, 1992.
- [3] M. Au et al. “In-source and in-trap formation of molecular ions in the actinide mass range at CERN-ISOLDE”. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 541:375–379, 2023.
- [4] R. Eder et al. “The production yields of radioactive ion-beams from fluorinated targets at the ISOLDE on-line mass separator”. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 62(4):535–540, 1992.
- [5] R. Bark and C. Fransen. “Development of $^{160,162,164}\text{Yb}$ beams: Coulomb Excitation of Triaxial Superdeformed “beta-bands” in light Yb isotopes”. Technical report, CERN, Geneva, 2021.
- [6] F. Borgna. “Terbium-149 for targeted alpha therapy”. Technical report, CERN, Geneva, 2021.
- [7] B. Olaizola et al. “Development of neutron-rich Tb beams for a systematic study approaching the doubly mid-shell in Rare-Earth nuclei”. Technical report, CERN, Geneva, 2020.
- [8] K. Chrysalidis et al. “Yield measurements for lanthanide elements with Ta- foil target and a LIST ion source”. Technical report, CERN, Geneva, 2022.
- [9] T. E. Cocolios. “Nuclear Shapes of Heavy Atoms and Proton-Emitting nuclei”. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101088504>.
- [10] B. Cheal et al. “Laser spectroscopy of neutron-deficient thulium isotopes”. Technical report, CERN, Geneva, 2022.
- [11] S. Freeman and D. Sharp. “Beam development for a study of the evolution of single-neutron states outside the N=82 core using ^{146}Gd , ^{148}Dy and $^{150}\text{Er}(\text{dp})$.” Technical report, CERN, Geneva, 2021.
- [12] E. Nacher. “Off-line TAS measurements of the long-lived nuclei $^{152,155}\text{Tb}$ and $^{76,77}\text{Br}$ for their relevance in medicine and neutrino physics”. Technical report, CERN, Geneva, 2022.
- [13] M. A. Nagl. “A new tool for the search of nuclides with properties suitable for nuclear solid state physics based on the Evaluated Nuclear Structure Data Files”. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 726:17–30, 2013.

- [14] C. Müller et al. “Future prospects for SPECT imaging using the radiolanthanide terbium-155 production and preclinical evaluation in tumor-bearing mice”. *Nuclear medicine and biology*, 41:e58–e65, 2014.
- [15] C. Müller et al. “Direct in vitro and in vivo comparison of ^{161}Tb and ^{177}Lu using a tumour-targeting folate conjugate”. *European journal of nuclear medicine and molecular imaging*, 41(3):476–485, 2014.
- [16] C. Müller et al. “Alpha-PET with terbium-149: evidence and perspectives for radiotheragnostics”. *EJNMMI radiopharmacy and chemistry*, 1(1):1–5, 2017.
- [17] C. Müller et al. “A unique matched quadruplet of terbium radioisotopes for PET and SPECT and for α - and β -radionuclide therapy: an in vivo proof-of-concept study with a new receptor-targeted folate derivative”. *Journal of nuclear medicine*, 53(12):1951–1959, 2012.
- [18] NuPECC. “Nuclear Physics for Medicine”, 2014.
- [19] U. Köster et al. “On-line yields obtained with the ISOLDE RILIS”. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 204:347–352, 2003.
- [20] ISOL@MYRRHA. isolmyrrha.sckcen.be/en/Introduction.
- [21] TATTOOS. psi.ch/en/impact/tattoos.
- [22] B Leenders et al. “On the feasibility of online terbium extraction at ISOL@ MYRRHA”. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 541:249–252, 2023.
- [23] R. Wolf. “First on-line applications of multi-reflection time-of-flight mass separator at ISOLTRAP and the mass measurement of ^{82}Zn ”. PhD thesis, Greifswald U., 2013.
- [24] S. Stegemann et al. “The CERN-ISOLDE fast tape station”. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 541:169–172, 2023.
- [25] S. Kreim et al. “Recent exploits of the ISOLTRAP mass spectrometer”. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 317:492–500, 2013.

DESCRIPTION OF THE PROPOSED EXPERIMENT

Please describe here below the main parts of your experimental set-up:

Part of the experiment	Design and manufacturing
If relevant, write here the name of the <u>fixed</u> installation you will be using [Name fixed/present ISOLDE installation: ISOLTRAP, Tape station, GLM beamline]	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To be used without any modification <input type="checkbox"/> To be modified
If relevant, describe here the name of the <u>flexible/transported</u> equipment you will bring to CERN from your Institute [Part 1 of experiment/ equipment]	<input type="checkbox"/> Standard equipment supplied by a manufacturer <input type="checkbox"/> CERN/collaboration responsible for the design and/or manufacturing
[Part 2 of experiment/ equipment]	<input type="checkbox"/> Standard equipment supplied by a manufacturer <input type="checkbox"/> CERN/collaboration responsible for the design and/or manufacturing
[insert lines if needed]	

HAZARDS GENERATED BY THE EXPERIMENT

Additional hazard from flexible or transported equipment to the CERN site:

Domain	Hazards/Hazardous Activities	Description
Mechanical Safety	Pressure	<input type="checkbox"/> [pressure] [bar], [volume][l]
	Vacuum	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Machine tools	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Mechanical energy (moving parts)	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Hot/Cold surfaces	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cryogenic Safety	Cryogenic fluid	<input type="checkbox"/> [fluid] [m3]
Electrical Safety	Electrical equipment and installations	<input type="checkbox"/> [voltage] [V], [current] [A]
	High Voltage equipment	<input type="checkbox"/> [voltage] [V]
Chemical Safety	CMR (carcinogens, mutagens and toxic to reproduction)	<input type="checkbox"/> [fluid], [quantity]
	Toxic/Irritant	<input type="checkbox"/> [fluid], [quantity]
	Corrosive	<input type="checkbox"/> [fluid], [quantity]
	Oxidizing	<input type="checkbox"/> [fluid], [quantity]
	Flammable/Potentially explosive atmospheres	<input type="checkbox"/> [fluid], [quantity]
	Dangerous for the environment	<input type="checkbox"/> [fluid], [quantity]
Non-ionizing radiation Safety	Laser	<input type="checkbox"/> [laser], [class]
	UV light	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Magnetic field	<input type="checkbox"/> [magnetic field] [T]
	Excessive noise	<input type="checkbox"/>

Workplace

	Working outside normal working hours	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Working at height (climbing platforms, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Outdoor activities	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Fire Safety	Ignition sources	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Combustible Materials	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Hot Work (e.g. welding, grinding)	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Other hazards			